

ACTION OF SODIUM ON ETHYL β -METHYLBUTANE- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -TRICARBOXYLATE PART I

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Contrary to the observations of Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1548), it is now found that ethyl 4-methylcyclopentan-1-one-2 : 4-dicarboxylate constitutes the chief product of the sodium condensation of ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate.

The subject matter of the present investigation originated in some experiments which were carried out with the object of synthesising the keto-ester (I).

A convenient starting point for this purpose appeared to be provided by ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate (II, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$), which was first prepared by Ruzicka (*Ber.*, 1917, 80, 136a) in connection with his well known synthesis of fenchone.

The Dieckmann cyclisation of (II, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$) can obviously occur in two ways, giving the cyclopentanone esters (III, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{R} = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$) and (III, $R = R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$). Ruzicka did not, however, consider it necessary to determine the constitution of this ester, since, on hydrolysis either structure would yield 3-methylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic acid (III, $R = R_1 = R_2 = \text{X} = \text{H}$), which was the required intermediate in the fenchone synthesis.

Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1548) appears to have established definitely that the initial condensation product must be represented by (III, $R = R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$); since on careful oxidation with potassium permanganate it gave α -methylglutaric acid, a liquid acid, analysis of the silver salt of which corresponded with that of α -hydroxy- α -methylglutaric acid, and a trace of succinic acid. No trace of either β -methyltricarballic acid or of methylsuccinic acid, the products which would result from the oxidation of an ester of structure (III, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{R} = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$) could be detected.

It was, therefore, hoped that the products of the sodium condensation of (II, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$) on treatment with methyl iodide would afford the desired keto-ester (I). Curiously enough the methylated keto-ester actually isolated from the products of the above condensation on hydrolysis with alcoholic potash yielded β -methylpentane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (II, $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{X} = \text{H}$), m.p. 178-79° (*phenylphenacyl* ester, m.p. 158°), identical with a synthetic specimen described below. It follows, therefore that the methylated keto-ester should be best represented by the structure (III, $R = \text{Me}$; $R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$). Moreover, the latter on treatment with sodium ethylate solution furnished ethyl β -methylpentane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate (II, $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$), which on cyclisation with sodium gives ethyl 2 : 4-dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-4 : 5-dicarboxylate (III, $R = \text{H}$; $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$). This on hydrolysis with dilute acids affords 2 : 4-dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-4-carboxylic acid (III, $R = R_2 = \text{X} = \text{H}$; $R_1 = \text{Me}$) as a liquid, of which the semicarbazone melts at 173° alone or in admixture with an authentic specimen.

Synthesis of β -Methylpentane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylic Acid (II, $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{X} = \text{H}$) and of 2:4-Dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-4-carboxylic Acid (III, $R = R_2 = \text{X} = \text{H}$; $R_1 = \text{Me}$).

Ethyl α -methylacrylate (IV) has been condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of acetamide and acetic acid (Cope, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2329) to give ethyl α -cyano- β -methyl- Δ^4 -pentene- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (V). This reacts with hydrogen cyanide with the formation of ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -methylpentane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (VI) (*cf.* Hope and Sheldon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2223; Lapworth and McRea, *ibid.*, p. 2752; Bardhan and Ganguly, *ibid.*, 1936, 1852). The latter on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid affords (II, $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{X} = \text{H}$), m.p. 178-79°. The ethyl ester (II, $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$) on sodium condensation gives (III, $R = \text{H}$; $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$), which on hydrolysis with ditute acids furnishes (III, $R = R_2 = \text{X} = \text{H}$; $R_1 = \text{Me}$) which has been characterised by the formation of a semicarbazone. m.p., 173°.

γ -Methylpentane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (II, $R_2 = \text{Me}$; $R_1 = \text{X} = \text{H}$), which might have been formed by the hydrolysis of the keto-ester having the alternative structure (I), has already been described by Sen-Gupta (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 343). The ester of this acid on cyclisation followed by hydrolysis in the usual way, however, furnishes a liquid keto-acid (III, $R = \text{X} = R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{Me}$), the semicarbazone of which had m.p. 208° and thus differs markedly from the corresponding product derived from the isomeric keto-acid (III, $R = \text{X} = \text{H}$; $R_1 = \text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$) described above.

It follows, therefore, that the action of sodium on ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate leads to the formation of ethyl 3-methylcyclopentan-1-one-3:5-dicarboxylate (III, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $R = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$) and not the isomeric ethyl 3-methylcyclopentan-1-one-2:3-dicarboxylate (III, $R = R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$), as suggested by Baker (*loc. cit.*).

On searching the literature which has special reference to the Dieckmann condensation of analogously constituted tricarboxylic esters it is found that Perkin and Thorpe (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 781) isolated the keto-ester (VIII, $R = \text{Me}$) as the sole product of the condensation of ethyl $\beta\beta$ -dimethylbutane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylate (VII, $R = \text{Me}$) with sodium.

Similarly, Kay and Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 1645) showed that the action of sodium on ethyl butane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ tricarboxylate (VII, $R = \text{H}$) leads to the formation of ethyl cyclopentan-1-one-2:4-dicarboxylate (IX). On the other hand, Ruzicka, Borges de Almeida and Brack (*Hebr. Chim. Acta*, 1934, 17, 183) showed that in the condensation both the possible isomeric keto-esters (IX) and (VIII, $R = \text{H}$) are formed.

These experiments are significant from the point of view of the present investigation, as relatively small quantities of the keto-ester (III, $R = R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $\text{X} = \text{Et}$) may also

accompany the isomeric ester (III, $R_1=R_2=H$; $R=CO_2Et$; $X=Et$), which apparently constitutes the sole product of the reaction. This must, however, remain an open question until further experiments, which are in hand, have been performed

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate, required for this work, was prepared according to Ruzicka (*loc. cit.*), with a slight modification (*cf.* Sen-Gupta, *loc. cit.*), by condensing ethyl laevulate with ethyl bromoacetate in presence of zinc in benzene. The lactonic ester, thus obtained, was heated to 200-220° for 10 hours with $1\frac{1}{2}$ mol. of finely powdered potassium cyanide and the brown reaction product hydrolysed by heating on a sand-bath for 10 hours with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The solution was then evaporated to dryness and the residue extracted with ether. The crude acid obtained on evaporation of the ether was esterified by the alcohol-vapour method when ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate was obtained as a colourless mobile liquid, b. p. 142°/4mm.

Sodium Condensation of Ethyl β -Methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate and Methylation of the Sodio-salt: Formation of the Keto-ester (III, $R=CO_2Et$; $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$; $X=Et$).—Ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate (36 g.) was heated on the water-bath with a suspension of finely divided sodium (3.5 g.) in dry benzene (90 c.c.). A vigorous evolution of hydrogen started on heating and the reaction was complete in 45 minutes. It was then cooled in ice and methyl iodide (12 c.c.) was added and kept over-night. The next day, it was refluxed for 16 hours with the addition of a little methyl iodide from time to time. The product was treated with water, the benzene layer was separated, washed and the benzene evaporated. The product obtained was then distilled as a colourless liquid, b. p. 135°/6 mm, yield 26 g. It gave no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 60.6; H, 7.7. $C_{18}H_{20}O_8$ requires C, 60.9; H, 7.8 per cent).

Acid Hydrolysis of the Methylated Product: Formation of β -Methylpentane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic Acid (II, $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$; $X=H$).—The above product (10 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 3 hours with potassium hydroxide (10 g.) in 25% aqueous alcoholic solution. The alcohol was then evaporated off on the water-bath with the addition of water. It was then acidified and extracted with ether. The solid acid obtained on evaporation of the ether was crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid. The *pure* acid melted at 178-179° and there was no depression of the melting point when it was mixed with an authentic specimen. (Found: C, 49.2; H, 6.5. $C_9H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 49.5; H, 6.4 per cent).

Formation of (II, $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$; $X=Et$) *from the Methylated Keto-ester* (III, $R=CO_2Et$; $R_1=Me$; $R_2=H$; $X=Et$).—The methylated keto-dicarboxylic ester (15 g.) was refluxed on the water-bath for 4 hours with a solution of sodium (0.35 g.) in absolute alcohol (16 c.c.). It was treated with water, acidified and extracted with ether, and the residual oil obtained on evaporation of the ether was distilled *in vacuo*, when with the exception of a little low boiling product (1.4 g), it boiled constantly at 140-42°/5 mm., yield 14.3 g.

Cyclisation of the Triethylester obtained above: Formation of (III, $R=H$; $R_1=Me$; $R_2=CO_2Et$; $X=Et$).—The above ester was heated on the water-bath with a suspension of molecular sodium (1.3 g.) in dry benzene (35 c.c.). The reaction started after heating for 10 minutes and was complete in an hour. The product was treated with water, acidified with

ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid and the benzene layer separated. The benzene solution was washed with water and the benzene evaporated. The product was then distilled at $130\text{--}33^\circ/6\text{mm.}$ yield 9.3 g. It gives a strong colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 60.4; H, 7.8. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 60.9; H, 7.8 per cent).

Hydrolysis of the above Keto-ester to 2:4-Dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-4-carboxylic Acid (III, $\text{R}_1=\text{R}_2=\text{X}=\text{H}$; $\text{R}=\text{Me}$).—The above ester (9 g.) was heated on a sand-bath for 6 hours with 10 volumes of 6% hydrochloric acid. The clear solution was neutralised with sodium carbonate and extracted with ether to remove any neutral matter. It was then acidified, saturated with salt and extracted with ether. The liquid keto-acid obtained on evaporation of the ether was converted into the semicarbazone. The semicarbazone melted at 173° (decomp.) after two crystallisations from methyl alcohol, and there was no depression of the melting point on mixing it with an authentic sample. (Found: C, 50.4; H, 7.0. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ requires C, 50.7; H, 7.0 per cent).

Synthesis of β -Methylpentane- $\alpha\beta\beta$ -tricarboxylic Acid (II, $\text{R}_1=\text{Me}$; $\text{R}_2=\text{X}=\text{H}$) and 2:4-Dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-4-carboxylic Acid (III, $\text{R}_1=\text{Me}$; $\text{R}_2=\text{X}=\text{R}=\text{H}$).

Ethyl α -acetyl- β -methylsuccinate.—Ethyl aceto-acetate (32.5 g.) was added dropwise to an ice-cold suspension of finely divided sodium (5.75 g.) in benzene (65 c.c.) and the solution kept over-night. It was then treated with ethyl α -bromopropionate (45.5 g.) and heated on the water-bath for 20 hours and worked up in the usual way, b.p. $120^\circ/5\text{mm.}$, yield 37g.

Ethyl α -Methylaevulate (IV)—The above product was hydrolysed by heating on a sand-bath for 8 hours with 5 volumes of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:2). The clear solution obtained was then evaporated to dryness. The dry residue (17 g.) was esterified by refluxing for 10 hours with absolute alcohol (80 c.c.) and 8 c.c. of alcoholic hydrogen chloride (saturated at 0°). The alcohol was then distilled off and the residue taken up in ether, washed with water, dried over calcium chloride, and the solvent evaporated. The residue was then distilled at $85^\circ/7\text{mm.}$, yield 16 g.

Ethyl α -Cyano- β -methyl- Δ^4 -pentene- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (V).— α -Methyl aevulic ester (15.2 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (11.3 g.), acetamide (2 g.) and glacial acetic acid (30 c.c.) were taken in a flask provided with a short fractionating column. The acetic acid was distilled off slowly during 4-5 hours, so that the temperature of the vapour was always between 105° and 115° . It was then taken up in ether, washed well with water and the ether was evaporated. The residual liquid on distillation gave 14.5 g. of the unsaturated cyanoester, b.p. $148^\circ/5\text{mm.}$ (Found: C, 61.5; H, 7.4. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires C, 61.6; H, 7.5 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -Dicyano- β -methylpentane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (VI).—The unsaturated cyano-ester (14.1g.) was dissolved in spirit (68 c.c.) and treated with a solution of potassium cyanide (7.2 g.) in water (39 c.c.). The warm product was then cooled in ice-water, treated, drop by drop, with 15.2 c.c. of 20% hydrochloric acid, and kept for 45 minutes. The product was diluted with a large volume of water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The oil separating was extracted with ether and washed with water. The oily liquid, obtained on distillation of the solvent, was distilled at $176^\circ/5\text{mm.}$, yield 13.5 g. (Found: C, 59.7; H, 7.1. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires C, 60.0; H, 7.1 per cent).

β -Methyl pentane- $\alpha\beta\beta$ -tricarboxylic Acid (II, $\text{R}_1=\text{Me}$; $\text{R}_2=\text{X}=\text{H}$) was prepared from the dicyano ester (13.3 g.) by heating on a sand-bath for 12 hours with concentrated hydrochloric acid (75 c.c.). The clear solution obtained was evaporated to dryness on the water-bath and the solid residue was extracted with ether. On evaporation of the solvent the product

solidified. The dry residue (10 g.) was esterified by dissolving in absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (2.5 c.c.) and heating for 6 hours at 210° in a current of hot alcohol vapour. The product was then worked up and distilled at $140^\circ/4$ mm., yield 10 g. (Found : C, 59.4 ; H, 8.6. $C_{15}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 59.6 ; H, 8.6 per cent).

The ethyl ester (1.5 g.) was heated on a sand-bath with 10 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid till a clear solution was obtained. It was then evaporated to dryness. The acid (II, $R_1=Me$; $R_2=X=H$) was obtained on crystallisation of the residue several times from concentrated hydrochloric acid, m.p. $178-9^\circ$. It is readily soluble in water and hot concentrated hydrochloric acid but sparingly soluble in ether and cold concentrated hydrochloric acid. (Found : C, 49.4 ; H 6.5. $C_9H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 49.5 ; H, 6.4 per cent).

The *p*-phenylphenacyl ester crystallises from a mixture of benzene and absolute alcohol, m.p. 158° . (Found : C, 76.4 ; H, 5.6. $C_{21}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 76.5 ; H, 5.5 per cent).

Ethyl 2 : 4-Dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-4 : 5-dicarboxylate (III, $R=H$; $R_1=Me$; $R_2=CO_2Et$; $X=Et$).—The triethyl ester (7.9 g.) was heated on a water-bath with a fine suspension of sodium (0.72 g.) in dry benzene (20 c.c.). The reaction started after 10 minutes and was complete in 45 minutes. It was treated with ice-water and acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The upper benzene layer was separated, washed well with water and the benzene distilled completely under reduced pressure. The product boiled at $126^\circ/4$ mm., yield 4.5 g. It gives a violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 60.7 ; H, 7.6. $C_{18}H_{26}O_7$ requires C, 60.9 ; H, 7.8 per cent).

2:4-Dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-4-carboxylic Acid (III, $R_1=R_2=X=H$; $R=Me$).—The above product (4.2 g.) was heated on a sand-bath for 6-7 hours with 50 c.c. of 6% hydrochloric acid. The clear solution was neutralised with sodium carbonate and extracted with ether to remove any neutral matter. The aqueous solution was then acidified, saturated with salt and extracted with ether. The acid (III, $R_1=R_2=X=H$; $R=Me$) (2.3 g.) was obtained as a liquid on evaporation of the ether. The *semicarbazone* crystallises from methyl alcohol, m.p. 173° (decomp.). (Found : C, 50.4 ; H, 7.0. $C_9H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires C, 50.7 ; H, 7.0 per cent).

Further work is in progress.

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